

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF GEL FOR THE TREATMENT OF NASAL POLYPS

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ABSTRACT

Nasal polyps (NP) are benign lesions arising from the mucosa of nasal sinuses (commonly at the outflow tract of one or more sinuses or from mucosa of nasal cavity). Having an uncertain aetiology and a tendency to recur, their diagnosis as well as treatment is very challenging. Management of nasal polyps by otolaryngologist is highly demanding. If not treated, they become very painful due to associated inflammation and irritation. **Mainly the** Causes of nasal polyps- Chronic rhinitis, Recurring infection, Allergies, Drug sensitivity. Nasal polyps was used to treat by traditional method which includes Steam inhalation, Use of apple cider vinegar, Use of turmeric powder, Intake of garlic, Tea tree oil, Use of pepper, Intake of pineapple, Application of castor oil, Breathing exercise. Modern treatment for nasal polyps includes medical and surgical treatment. The medical treatment includes use of

Corticosteroids like Flonase, Rhinocort, Nasacort, Mometas furoate and surgical treatment includes Endoscopic sinus surgery. The use of corticosteroids shows severe side symptoms weight gain, mood changes, and increased appetite. More serious side effects can include high blood pressure, osteoporosis, and increased risk of infection. **Nasal gel** gives the targeted drug delivery to the nasal mucosa, potentially improving absorption. Additionally, nasal gels can protect the drug from enzymatic degradation and offer sustained release, leading to enhanced patient compliance and a potentially rapid onset of action. Also gel

dosage form is easy formulation and non-greasy application, contributing to long-term stability also it is cost and time conservative.

KEYWORDS: Nasal polyps, gel formulation & its assessment, corticosteroids, etc.

INTRODUCTION

Fig. 1: Nasal Polyps.

In general population, the prevalence of nasal polyp is considered to be around 4%. In cadaveric studies, this prevalence has been reported as high as 40%. They pre-dominantly affect adults and usually present in patients older than 20. They are uncommon in children under 10 and may be presenting feature of cystic fibrosis. There is at least 2:1 male to female ratio. Many of patients of nasal polyp suffer from asthma.

Aetiology of nasal polyps

Some theories propose polyps as a consequence of chronic inflammation in the nose and nasal sinuses characterized by stromal oedema and variable cellular infiltrate. Historically, it has been assumed that allergy is pre-disposed to nasal polyps because the symptoms of watery rhinorrhoea and mucosal swelling were present in both diseases along with abundance of eosinophil in the nasal secretion. In many cases the initiating cause may be different.

Treatment for nasal polyps

Nasal polyps was used to treat by traditional method which includes Steam inhalation, Use of apple cider vinegar, Use of turmeric powder, Intake of garlic, Tea tree oil, Use of pepper, Intake of pineapple, Application of castor oil, Breathing exercise.

Table No. 1: Traditional methods used for treatment of nasal polyps.

Use of apple cider vinegar	It is most effective remedy inhalation of the steam of apple cider vinegar. 10ml vinegar mixed with hot water and inhales his steam throughout the day. It washes out the bacteria and infectious material from nostril and relieve in nasal congestion	Anti-inflammatory and reduce nasal congestion
Use of turmeric powder	Turmeric has strong anti-inflammatory, anti-septic anti-pyretic properties. One tablespoon of turmeric powder should be mixed with one glass of hot milk and have it twice a day. It accelerates the healing process and reduces the production of extra mucus from nasal cavity.	Anti-inflammatory
Intake of garlic	Garlic has high antiseptic and antioxidant properties. It removes the infectious material and prevents the growth of nasal polyps. It also helps in mucus drainage. Take finely chopped garlic with hot water twice a day for better results.	Prevents growth of polyps.
Tea tree oil	It has high antibiotic activity and help in shortening of the polyp. Take cotton wool and dip it into in oil and put it into the affected nostril prevents the recurrence of this disease.	Shortening of polyps and anti-inflammatory.
Use of pepper	A cayenne pepper contains high concentration of capsaicin. This chemical has capacity to reduce the extra growth in nostril. It is good for intense headache associated with nasal polyps	Reduce headache
Intake of pineapple	Pineapple contain substance known as bromelain which helps to destroy the extra cells and decreases the size of polyp. Sinus cavity immunity is well maintained by frequent and regular intake of this fruit.	Size reduction
Application of castor oil	Consume one or two tablespoon daily reduces the risk of occurrence. It is best to take it orally, it eliminates the moisture content if the polyp and makes it dry. Once it becomes dry then it reduces in size. It also strengthens the Immune system of human. It also kills the bacteria and fungus which are responsible for it.	Size reduction

Breathing exercise	Breathing exercises help by reducing congestion and other symptoms of nasal polyps. Bhramarj-pranayama can opens sinuses. These exercises also help to control breathing issue.	Reduce nasal congestion.
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Modern treatment

Modern treatment for nasal polyps includes medical and surgical treatment. The medical treatment includes use of Corticosteroids like Flonase, Rhinocort, Nasacort, Mometas--one furoate and surgical treatment includes Endoscopic sinus surgery.

OBJECTIVES

Formulation and evaluation of gel for the treatment of nasal polyps using gel technology.

The objective would be achieved by following the steps

1. Characterization of tea tree oil for ascertaining identity, purity, quality, and safety.
2. Characterization of selected formulation additives for establishing their identity, quality, and their compatibility with tea tree oil for the formulation of gel.
3. Formulation of non-medicated and medicated gel with varying types and concentrations of additives.
4. Evaluation of gel for physicochemical, cosmetic, and functional characteristics.
5. Assessment of stability of the optimized gel formulation/s.

METHODOLOGY: materials and method

Table No. 1.1: Actives & formulation additives.

Sr. No.	Name of the chemical	Purpose/Role in the Experiment
1.	Tea tree oil i.e melaleuca alterfolia	Shows strong anti-inflammatory ction.
3.	Non –ionic carboxy vinyl polymer –(Carbomer) grade 934	Gelling agent in gel formulation
4.	Polymer sodium alginate	Gelling agent in gel formulation
5.	Polyethylene glycol 300 (PEG 300)	Emulsifier/ Humectant in hydrogel formulation
6.	Methanol (99.8 %) (MeOH)	Chem Avi Industries, Mumbai
7.	Mannitol(C ₆ H ₁₄ O ₆)	Maintaining tonicity
8.	Phosphate buffer (6.4)	Maintaining pH

In these polymers gelling consistency loses as the temperature and pH changes

Hence, polymeric combination used like-

- **Carbopol + sodium alginate** (0.1+0.1,0.2+0.1,0.1+0.2) – shown good gelling activity at required pH.
- **Table No. 1.2: Formulation of gel containing tea tree oil.**

Sr. No.	API/Excipients	Concentration of ingredient (% w/w)&(%w/v)
1.	<i>Tea tree oil</i>	1.00
3.	Carbomer 934 (%w/v)	0.3
4.	Sodium alginate (%w/v)	0.1
5.	PEG 300	1.25
6.	Mannitol	2.5
7.	Methanol	5 ml
8.	Phosphate buffer 6.4	1 ml
9.	Distilled water	Q.S. to 25g

Method of preparation

The formulation is prepared by dissolving the drug tea tree oil (1% w/w) concentration in 10 ml of methanol and taken 10 ml of distilled water which was kept on stirring. Then the polymeric solution of Carbopol and sodium alginate in the ratio of 3:1 were taken and added to above solution. In that solution as mentioned above specified quantities of mannitol and PEG 300 added. Resultant solution were stirred for 15 minutes. And to maintain pH buffer solution of 6.4 added to above solution and distilled water of required quantity.

A) Evaluation parameters

Table No.1.3: List of evaluation parameters for gel formulation.

Sr.No.	Parameters/ Test	Procedures
General description		
1.	Physical state/ Appearance	For this, gel was placed into watch glass and observed for appearance and presence of foreign organic matter with unaided eyes as well as with magnifying glass.
2.	Homogeneity	The gels were examined for their physical properties like colour, clarity and phase separation by visual inspection. They are tested for the presence of any aggregates.
Organoleptic		
3.	Colour	For this, gel was placed into watch glass and observed for colour by subjective visual perception.
4.	Odour	For this, gel was placed into watch glass and its

		odour was sensed by subjective olfactory perception.
5.	Texture	For this, gel was placed into the palm and texture was sensed by touch using middle figure and thumb.
Physicochemical		
6.	pH	The pH of hydrogel formulations was determined by using digital pH meter. 1 g of gel was dissolved in 100 ml distilled water. The measurement of pH of each formulation was done in triplicate and average values are calculated.
7.	Viscosity	The measurement of viscosity of the prepared gel was done with a Brookfield Viscometer. The gels were rotated at 10-100 rotations per minute at 25°C by using the spindle 94.
8.	Spreadability	The relative spreadability of hydrogels recorded in terms of diameter covered by the film formed due to spreading. Following the procedure described previously
9.	Skin irritation test (HET Cam test)	For this test a fertilized egg of hen of 9 days taken. Also 1% concentratic solution of sodium lauryl sulphate(SLS) prepared as a reference sample and drug solution taken. The irritation can be determined by coagulation in the blood cells of fertizeed egg.
10.	Drug content assay	One ml of the prepared formulation was dispersed in 10 ml of methanol for 2–3 min with occasional shaking. The resulting solution was filtered through a 0.45 µm filter paper and was diluted with methanol. The amount of loratadine in the formulation was determined spectrophotometrically at 280 nm
11.	In-vitro drug release	<i>In vitro</i> drug release of loratadine was determined using Franz-diffusion cell. The sheep nasal mucosa was prepared as described in the above procedures. The prepared nasal mucosa was mounted between the donor and receptor compartments. The receptor compartment was filled with phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) at 37 °C. The solution was stirred at 100 rpm. The gel (10 mg) was placed on the nasal mucosa and the compartments were clamped together. One ml of the sample was withdrawn at predetermined time intervals (0, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 h) from receptor compartments and immediately replaced using phosphate buffer (pH 6.4). After filtering through 0.45 µm filter and appropriate dilution, the samples were analyzed for drug content at 280 nm
12.	Stability study	Short-term stability study of prepared in-situ formulation was carried out by storing at 27±2°C for a period of three weeks. At intervals of one week the gel was visually examined for any physical changes.
13.	Gelling time and gelling temperature	The gelling time was determined by placing the test tube, containing sufficient quantity of the prepared

		<p>solutions, in a water bath at 4 °C. The temperature of water bath was increased slowly at a constant rate of 1 °C every 2 min.</p> <p>The sol-gel transition temperature (Tsol-gel) of the prepared gel formulations was evaluated by transferring 2 ml of the prepared formulation to a test tube (10 ml). After sealing with a parafilm, the tube was kept in a circulation water bath at 37 °C. Following each temperature setting, equilibration was allowed for 10 min. Finally, the test tube was placed horizontally to observe the state of the sample and to examine the gelation.</p>
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B) RESULTS

Table No. 1.5: Characteristics of placebo gel formulation.

Sr. No.	Parameters	C1 (1:1)	C2 (2:1)	C3 (3:1)	C4 (4:1)	C5 (5:1)
1.	Appearance	Clear	Clear	Clear	coagulation	lump
2.	Homogeneity	+++	+++	+++	++	--
3.	Colour	Colourless	Colourless	Colourless	Colourless	Colourless
4.	Odour	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic
5.	Texture	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	lump	Coagulated gel
6.	pH	6.3	6.5	6.8	6.7	6.5
7.	Viscosity (CPS)	-	-	-	-	-
8.	Spread ability (cms)	3.70	4.30	6.20	7.35	2.10
9.	Grittiness	-	-	-	-	-

Table 1.6: characteristics of formulation containing tea tree oil.

Sr. No.	Parameters	TTO3 (C3)
1.	Appearance	Clear
2.	Homogeneity	+++
3.	Colour	Colourless
4.	Odour	Characteristic
5.	Texture	Smooth
6.	pH	6.8
7.	Viscosity (CPS)	-
8.	Spread ability (cms)	7.26
9.	Gelling time	3-4 sec
10.	Gelling temperature	35+/- 2 *c
9.	Grittiness	-

10. Irritation test of tea tree oil in gel formulation revealed by HET CAM test (Hen’s Egg Test on The ChorioAllantoic Membrane)

Photo 8.2: HET CAM test of gel formulation containing tea tree oil (TTO)- C3 (TTO3)

11. In-vitro drug release

Table No. 1.7: drug release of gel containing tea tree oil.

Time (Hrs)	F3 (%CDR)
0	0
0.5	4.7.2
2	13.50
3	23.90
4	35.70
6	48.94

IN-vitro drug release of gel containing tea tree oil (TTO)- C3 formulation

12. Stability study

Table No. 1.8: stability studies of gel containing tea tree oil.

Duration	Temperature	Physical appearance	pH
After 8 days	27±2 °C	No change	6.7
After 15 days	27±2 °C	No change	6.5
After 30 days	27±2 °C	No change	6.4

C) DISCUSSION

Topical systems are promising for acne treatment due to adhesiveness property and direct contact with target areas. They offer prolonged release, enhanced absorption, and improved therapeutic outcomes for a given active.

In view of this, the present work has attempted to formulate a stable and safe topical delivery system of tea tree oil for treatment of nasal polyps.

1. Introduced an anti-inflammatory gel of melaleuca alterfolia (tea tree oil) a naturally available abundant material with bioactive compounds suitable for pharmaceutical products.
2. The study evaluated anti-inflammatory, and preservative properties of tea tree oil, establishing its potential as an effective anti-inflammatory agent.
3. Design of gel formulation considered properties of individual polymers
4. (carbomer934A+sodium alginate) as well as their co-relation that has influence on viscosity, pH, muco-adhesiveness and spreadability of the experimental gels.

Optimization: The optimized gel formulation exhibited desirable properties, indicating its potential as an effective anti-inflammatory gel..

5. Efficacy: The experimental findings demonstrated anti-inflammatory properties of the tea tree oil, suggesting its efficacy as an alternative to conventional polyps treatment facing issues of bacterial resistance.
6. Stability: The optimized formulation's stability study showed that the gel maintained its properties over time, ensuring a longer shelf life.

D) CONCLUSION

As the disease nasal polyps have only treatment with oral corticosteroids and surgery. They are having adverse side effects on the body. Thus the gel preparation can play a crucial role as an anti-inflammatory action in treatment of nasal polyps.

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